

UTAINA: CONNECTING AOTEAROA THROUGH DIGITISED SOUND AND STORY

Dr. Zak Argabrite

National Library of New
Zealand
New Zealand
Zak.Argabrite@dia.govt.nz
ORCID: 0009-0003-3782-
9218

Cynthia Wu

National Library of New
Zealand
New Zealand
Cynthia.Wu@dia.govt.nz
ORCID: 0000-0002-9318-275X

Joshua Ng

Archives New Zealand
New Zealand
Joshua.Ng@dia.govt.nz
ORCID: 0000-0001-7523-
2031

Delve into the impacts of Utaina, a multi-year collaborative digitisation project with the goal of preserving Aotearoa's at-risk audiovisual taonga. Over the course of the project, 70,000 digitised audiovisual materials have been made available virtually by the National Library and Archives New Zealand. Many items that have been digitised are culturally significant and unavailable to researchers elsewhere. For example, most of the music research requests through Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa's Virtual Reading Room (VRR) have been Pasifika music distributed on small labels in the 1970-90s such as Samoa Daystar Records, Polynesian Records, and Vision Recording Studio. The requests are primarily made by researchers conducting family research, wanting to connect with the music of their parents or grandparents. In most cases, the VRR provides the only copy these researchers can find on the internet. Our presentation will provide insights for how digitisation has helped to preserve the content stored on the at-risk items for future generations and reduced barriers to accessing them.

Submission Type – Poster

Keywords – Audiovisual, digitisation, access, communities,

Conference Topics – Please select 1 conference topic: Haerenga – Journey, Tūtaki – Encounter, or Tūhono – Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION

The combined audiovisual holdings of Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa – National Library of New Zealand and Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga – Archives New Zealand include the voices, stories, and

cultural knowledge of diverse communities. However, much of it is stored on fragile, legacy formats which are rapidly deteriorating. The Utaina project was established to respond to this urgent preservation challenge. Under this project, the National Library and Archives New Zealand are digitising more than 70,000 at-risk items and making them available to researchers in virtual reading rooms. This poster introduces the project's goals, partnerships, and progress to date, with a focus on how digitisation is supporting intergenerational connections, enhancing research access, and creating new pathways to audiovisual taonga previously hidden or inaccessible.

II. CONNECTING COMMUNITIES AND ENHANCING LITERACIES

Utaina is more than a digitisation effort—it provides opportunities for reconnection. Through the Virtual Reading Room, users across Aotearoa and globally can now access rare recordings, such as Pasifika music distributed on small labels in the 1970s–1990s, which are not available anywhere else online. These interactions highlight the project's role in cultural and information literacies, enabling users to rediscover their heritage, navigate archival systems, and engage with content meaningfully.

Utaina also demonstrates sustainable and inclusive digital preservation practice:

- Materials are described and tracked at scale through collaborative tools.

- Sensitive content is handled with care, balancing accessibility with privacy.
- File formats and workflows are chosen to support long-term preservation and access.

metadata extraction and configuration of Rosetta DNX (METS).

This poster reflects on how the project balances complexity and scale while improving the accessibility of Aotearoa's sounds and stories for future generations.

III. CONCLUSION

The Utaina project offers a valuable example of large-scale audiovisual preservation that balances technical robustness with improved access to culturally significant materials. By digitising and providing virtual access to at-risk content, the project has helped reduce barriers and supported communities in reconnecting with their histories. It highlights the potential of collaboration, inclusive access strategies, and preservation-informed decision-making in shaping sustainable digital memory practices.

As Utaina approaches completion, its influence extends beyond the number of hours digitised—offering useful insights into how institutions can scale preservation efforts while staying responsive to the needs of researchers, communities, and future users.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Zak Argabrite is the Logistics Coordinator for the Utaina Project. He is responsible for overseeing the inventory movement and location control of AV items in scope for digitisation at the National Library of New Zealand and Archives New Zealand.

Cynthia Wu is the Audiovisual Digitisation Leader at the National Library of New Zealand. She leads a team of subject matter experts across National Library and Archives to digitise and preserve their audiovisual collections and holdings under the Utaina project.

Joshua Ng, Digital Preservation Analyst, Archives New Zealand. His primary responsibility is to maintain the integrity of the Government Digital Archive. In Utaina, he was responsible in the research and design specifications for the process workflow including file formats identification, collection

